
JUDICIAL DETERMINATION OF RIGHTS OF THE EXPECTANT FATHER IN THE ABORTION CONUNDRUM: TRADITIONAL AND CONTEMPORARY PERCEPTION IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Pregnancy and its termination known as abortion has become a perennial topic of discourse. This has brought up several controversial issues, such as the rights of the expectant father in the abortion process which has been downplayed in virtually all jurisdictions. This has raised several questions in this research, for instance: should a pregnant woman be allowed and given the right to terminate the pregnancy without considering the interest of the expectant father? Using library-based approach which is doctrinal in nature, this article examined rights of the expectant father in abortion process from the traditional and contemporary perception as well as the judicial approach to the rights of the expectant father. The findings revealed that in virtually all jurisdictions, the expectant father has no right to prevent a pregnant woman from having an abortion and even has no right to be informed or consulted in respect of the proposed abortion. The laws on abortion in Nigeria do not address the rights of an expectant father in abortion process. It is however suggested that an expectant father should be vested with the rights to be informed or consulted irrespective of the reasons for the abortion procedure. But if it is health related, the right of the pregnant woman should outweigh the right of the expectant father. It was concluded that once a balance is struck between the pregnant woman and the expectant father, it will definitely take care of the interest of the expectant father in the abortion decision.

Keywords: Abortion, rights, expectant father, pregnant woman and judicial

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Human beings are bestowed with rights and in actualizing these rights there may be corresponding duties on others to observe or preserve the rights. In other words, rights may come in different perspectives which sometimes impose liability on other individual(s) to recognize these rights, and there may also be overlap or common grounds upon which rights are claimed by different individuals.¹ One of these situations is the rights of a woman to abortion and rights of the expectant father in the abortion process. The abortion debate is often perceived or portrayed as a clash or conflict of 'rights' - the rights of pregnant women to exercise control over their reproduction and that of the expectant father.²

Most abortion discourses largely dwell on the interest of the pregnant woman and the foetus, while the rights of expectant father are rarely considered.³ This should not be understood to mean that the expectant father has no interest in pregnancy. Then, should a pregnant woman be allowed and given the right to terminate the pregnancy without considering the interest of the expectant father? In certain situations, an expectant father may wish to preserve the life of his child, thereby refusing to allow abortion of the pregnancy.

In determining whether to permit abortion, there is need to consider the views of the expectant father. The rights and place of the husband or the man responsible for the pregnancy has been downplayed in virtually all jurisdictions, this is considered strange, and even it will be seen as anomaly in the Nigerian traditional societies where men and society dictate women's reproductive choices, rather than the women, who are directly affected by the decisions made on their behalf. Traditionally, men base their decisions on traditional, cultural and societal preconceived perceptions of women's place and worth in society. Traditional Nigerian society's perception of women's existence and essence in life is to bear children.⁴ In essence, traditionally, men have proprietary patriarchal powers and rights over females. These rights extend to men's control over the foetus growing inside women's bodies.

To exclude the father who has contributed to conception in the abortion decision-making process is not altogether desirable.⁵ The debate surrounding abortion is heated and tense, especially, the issue relating to the rights of the father in abortion cases renders the abortion topic all the more controversial.

The rights of the expectant father must be put into consideration subjectively within his socio-cultural environment in order to comprehend the intricate socio-legal issues bordering on abortion.⁶ However, this research will not concern itself with whether any of the parties to the abortion process is right or wrong; but examine and evaluate the viewpoints in respect of the place of the expectant father in abortion process in order to strike an acceptable balance of rights and interests in the abortion process.

¹F. Emiri, *Medical Law and Ethics in Nigeria*. 1st ed. (Lagos: Malthouse Press Limited, 2012) 133

²Sheila McLean, *Old Law, New Medicine: Medical ethics and human rights* (London and New York: Rivers Oram Press, 1999), 51-52

³ See statement of Daughtery J in *Davis v. Davis* (1992) 842 SW 2d 588

⁴W. Bascom, *The Yoruba of Southwest Nigeria* (New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston Inc., 1969), 62.

⁵F. Emiri, *Medical Law and Ethics in Nigeria*. 1st ed. (Lagos: Malthouse Press Limited, 2012) 143

⁶Titilayo Aderibigbe, 'Exploring the Competing Rights of Parties to Abortion Under Nigerian Law: The Decade In-Between' (2016) 1 Babcock University Socio-Legal Journal 48.

2.0 Fundamental issues

There are plethora of issues raising different questions such as whether the court should place the right of the pregnant woman above that of the expectant father or the husband with respect to taking the decision to abort. It is both a logical and biological fact that pregnancy entails the involvement of both man and woman. The fundamental questions now remain the determination of rights, such as the pregnant woman in exercising her right to abortion, will the consent of the husband or expectant father be required? If yes, what if both the parties disagree? Can the husband or expectant father seek injunction to stop his pregnant woman from terminating the pregnancy? If the pregnant woman insists on abortion, what is the social implication in a Nigerian family setting?

3.0 The place of the father: Judicial Approach

The legal position is well established in virtually all jurisdictions that the expectant father or father of the foetus has no right to prevent a pregnant woman from having an abortion and even has no right to be informed or consulted in respect of the proposed abortion.⁷ This was made clear by Supreme Court of the United States in *Planned Parenthood Central Missouri v. Danforth, Attorney-General of Missouri*⁸ that a husband, or an illegitimate father, has no right to stop his wife nor the woman *who is pregnant by him*, from carrying out a legal abortion. The court ruled that states were not required to notify or obtain permission from the husbands of women seeking abortion. The Court struck down as unconstitutional a restrictive Missouri abortion law which, inter alia, required the written consent of the husband before an abortion could be performed on a woman in the first trimester of her pregnancy unless a licensed physician certified that the abortion was necessary to preserve the mother's life.

In *Paton v. Trustees of British Pregnancy Advisory Services*,⁹ the court stated that a father cannot prevent a mother (his wife) from seeking an abortion. Sir George Baker of the Family Division of the Queen's Bench, said that the husband, therefore, in my view, has no legal right unforeseeable at law or in equity to stop his wife from having this abortion or to stop the doctor from carrying out the abortion. Paton was not satisfied with the decision, he therefore appealed to the European Commission of Human Rights¹⁰. He argued on appeal that his right under Article 8 of the European Convention on Human Right had been infringed, which permits respect of family life. The Commission rejected his appeal.¹¹ In dismissing his claim, it was pointed out that Article 8(2) clearly limits that right to that extent as necessary to protect the rights of the pregnant woman. It was held that the right of the mother prevails over that of the father because the woman is the person primarily affected or concerned with the pregnancy and its continuation.

This position taken in *Paton v. Trustees of BPAS*¹² in respect of the status of the expectant father was also endorsed in *C v S*¹³ as well in *Kelly v Kelly*¹⁴ where Scottish court rejected an application of a husband for an injunction to restrain his wife from having an abortion.

⁷F. Adeleke, *Comparative Abortion Jurisprudence: Reproductive Rights Paradigm*. 1st ed. (Ibadan: Sterling-Horden Limited, 2013) 195

⁸ (1976) 428 US 52

⁹ [1979] QB 276

¹⁰*Paton v United kingdom* (1980) 3 EHRR 408

¹¹ (1980) 3 EHRR 408 (E Com, HR)

¹²(1980) 3 EHRR 408

¹³(1988) QB 135

¹⁴ (1997) SLT 896

Similarly, in a Canadian case, *Tremblay v. Daigle*¹⁵ where it was argued that to the extent that a potential father contributes to conception, to that extent he should be vested with an equal say in the destiny of the foetus. The court in reply to the argument said that it does not appear to be any jurisprudential basis for this application or argument. No court in Quebec or elsewhere has ever accepted the argument that father's interest in a foetus which he helped to create could support a right to veto a woman's decision in respect of the foetus she is carrying. We have been unable to find a single decision in Quebec or elsewhere which would support the allegation of father's rights' necessary to support this injunction. There is nothing in the Civil Code or any legislation in Quebec which could be used to support the argument. This lack of legal basis is fatal to the argument about father's rights.¹⁶

The 'no-father right principle has been stretched to include the proposition that he cannot in any way act on behalf of the unborn to enforce its rights. The reason for this conclusion is based on the premise that a foetus has no legal right until it is born. It constitutes an integral part of its mother.¹⁷ It is apparent that in matters of abortion, the pregnant woman's right is paramount; she alone has the right to determine the fate of her foetus. But to exclude the father who has contributed to conception in the abortion process is not altogether desirable. In traditional or African societies, this position would be considered absurd and abnormal.¹⁸ While the law ought to accord primary consideration to the right of the mother, the views of the expectant father should not be treated as irrelevant either.¹⁹ If their wishes conflict, precedence can be given to the mother. The maintenance of matrimonial harmony is compelling reason for a consensus resolution framework. It is suggested that this should be an area of law that requires judicial rethinking. There is need for a balance to be struck.

It is imperative and pertinent to state that a husband or an expectant father cannot take any legal action either civil or criminal against the doctor who purportedly performs an abortion on his wife or pregnant woman without his consent or notification, such an action would not succeed as the doctor will rely on the provision of the law which does not require the consent of any one before legal abortion is performed on the pregnant woman to save her life and also rely on the rule of medical confidentiality guiding doctor and patient relationship. The fact that the woman is not a minor and is capable of giving an informed consent to the abortion may further lead to the failure of such a legal action.²⁰

4.0 The Place of the father: Traditional and Contemporary Perception in Nigeria

When a woman decides to terminate her pregnancy, different people will be affected or involved by the choice of abortion, for instance the expectant father. It is believed that since women are the bearers of children they ought to be the ones to decide on contraception, abortion and childbearing. But 'the law does not recognise unfettered rights of an individual

¹⁵ (1989) 62 DLR (4th) 534.

¹⁶ (1989) 62 DLR (4th) 634 (Can Sup. Ct).

¹⁷F. Emiri, *Medical Law and Ethics in Nigeria*. 1st ed. (Lagos: Malthouse Press Limited, 2012)142

¹⁸ *Ibid*

¹⁹ The Position of Paton case is the prevailing jurisprudence in common law jurisdiction. See Australian case of *AG of Queensland (exp Kerr) v. T*(1983) 46 ALR 275 (High C), Canadian case of *Borowski v. AG of Canada* [1987]4 WWR 385 (SaskCA), American case of *Roe v. Wade* 410 US 113 (1973), Quebec case of *Tremblay v. Daigle* (1989) 62 DLR (4th) 634 (Can Sup CL)

²⁰F. Adeleke, *Comparative Abortion Jurisprudence: Reproductive Rights Paradigm*. 1st ed. (Ibadan: Sterling-Horden Limited, 2013) 196

over his body in the same way as we have proprietary rights over objects we own²¹ What the law does allow is the freedom to use or refuse to use our bodies in such a way and to such extent that we do not violate public decency.²² Therefore women do not have the legally recognisable rights to use or misuse their bodies as they please.²³ This is the statutory held principle by British and Nigerian courts.

However, in Nigeria the concept of proprietary rights over women's bodies by someone supposedly holding a superior right over them come in conflict under traditional principles on the one hand, and Constitutional law on the other.²⁴ The traditional rights men had over women's bodies under traditional law differ under statutory laws applicable in Nigeria.²⁵ Constitutional law as it stands today in Nigeria accepts that there is equality of all persons²⁶ but traditional and Islamic law agree that husbands or fathers have some rights over their wives or daughters. Traditionally, men (whether husband or father) had proprietary patriarchal powers over females.²⁷ It seems these rights extend to men's control over the foetus growing inside women's bodies. This is because if men had the traditional right to dispose of women as chattels, or marry them off as they pleased, they therefore also had control over their bodies and consequently the foetus inside them as well.²⁸ Through the culture of patriarchy, Nigerian men seek to have access to, and control over, the pregnant female body even in modern times.

Patriarchy grants men ownership of the child when it is born and arguably, these rights extend to the foetus that the woman carries.²⁹ It is also not clear how far the constitutionally guaranteed autonomous freedom of all Nigerians extend in modern times to the body of the pregnant female who is a wife or daughter in practice.³⁰ In reality, it is believed the dominance of traditional and Islamic laws that accept the superiority of men over women

²¹R v Brown [1994] 1 AC 212; Carl F Stychin, 'Body Talk: Rethinking Autonomy, Commodification and the Embodied Legal Self in Sally Sheldon and Michael Thomson, *Feminist Perspectives on Health Care Law* (Cavendish Publishing Company, 1998), 211.

²²J. Harris 'Who owns my body' (1996) 16 OJLS 55 at 62

²³S. Munzer *A Theory of Property* (Cambridge: CUP: 1990), 37.

²⁴T. Aderibigbe, *My Womb Is Tired: A Socio-Legal Perspective Of The Reproductive Autonomy Of Women In South-West Nigeria With A Focus On Abortion*(Ph.D dissertation, Kent Law School, University Of Kent 2006)p.330

²⁵ Under traditional law, the concept of proprietary right which a father has over his child is predicated upon the notion that he owns his children. This gives him the right over his daughter's body, (not to abuse her sexually himself) but to treat her as he would any of his chattels.

²⁶ The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 section 17(2) (a) states: "every citizen shall have equality of rights, obligations and opportunities before the law"

²⁷ If a man has paid the bride price to the family of his bride and the woman subsequently decides to marry someone else. The suitor who has paid the bride price on her customarily is entitled to claim the children she may have for the new partner. This practice has been upheld by the Supreme Court as being repugnant to natural justice and good conscience *Edet v Essien* (1932) 11 NLR47.

²⁸ My assertions are made from a logical argument that if a woman is regarded in tradition as a chattel that a man has unfettered control over, (i.e. all that encompasses her as a human), (just as in the slavery days when a slave owner had unfettered 'right' to sell his slaves and their off-springs as he pleased), the man also had unfettered right over the foetus she carried.

²⁹ M. Klein, 'The Study of Slavery in Africa', (1978) *Journal of African History*, 602

³⁰ Legally a woman is autonomous, but the autonomy women enjoyed varied across different parts of Nigeria with women of the southern parts generally exercising more freedom and autonomy than women in the north parts of Nigeria: E. Isichei *A History of Nigeria* (London, Lagos & New York: Longman Group Limited, 1983), 257-259.

obscure the fundamental autonomous freedom of women under the Constitution in Nigeria.³¹ It is therefore stated, that this superficial autonomous freedom over their body by women exists only in law but not in reality.

Nigerian men with the backing of culture seek to control what women can and cannot do to their bodies in order to protect the foetus they carry.³² In practice, (but not under medical regulation) doctors insist that the husband of the pregnant woman (or the expectant father or father of the pregnant unmarried girl) sign the consent form for an abortion and not the adult female or other female relation of the pregnant woman or girl.³³ In essence, medicine recognises the superiority of the claim of men over women in cases of abortion even though the foetus is within the control of women's bodies and adult male and females are recognised as having equal status constitutionally.

Coming to modern times, patriarchy is still the socially and politically adopted forms of social relationship in Nigeria. On it hinges many other forms of social and traditional devolution and it has formed the bases of many modern laws in Nigeria. Patriarchy in Nigeria is archaic, even though it was often interpreted in ancient times to give men unfettered control over women, including their bodies; to maintain the social order, women had to procreate and were forbidden to dispose of the child in traditional society unless their own life might be lost in the process of termination. This forms the basis of acceptance of abortion law in Nigeria, which tallied, with the Victorian patriarchal concept in England where it originates.³⁴ Women's rights were therefore subsumed in the rights of the child they carried. However, in contemporary Nigeria, (as in traditional times), women have always resisted total control of their bodies by men and have often taken the initiative to control conception sometimes without men's knowledge. Nevertheless, in modern Nigerian society it is an acceptable fact that legally each individual controls his or her body.³⁵

5.0 Place of the father: Nigerian socio- legal perspective

The policy statement of the Nigerian government on the 'role and responsibilities of men in family life'³⁶ states that men are considered as the head of the family in our society and they take several decisions, especially the family size and bear greater paternalistic burden in caring for the family.³⁷ This indicates that men have powerful control over the family including making procreative choices for women. This policy statement shows that women are not expected to make independent choices about their fertility and procreation, that choice is within the absolute domain of men. Despite this, Nigerian women would not readily give birth to a child if the expectant father would not take responsibility for the pregnancy and

³¹ Titilayo Aderibigbe 'Women's Rights: Law and Practice in Nigeria' in Layi Erinsho; Babatunde Osotimehin and Janice E. Olawoye Women's Empowerment and Reproductive Health (Nigeria: Social Sciences and Reproductive Health Research Network, 1996), 48-49

³² T. Aderibigbe, My Womb Is Tired: A Socio-Legal Perspective Of The Reproductive Autonomy Of Women In South-West Nigeria With A Focus On Abortion (Ph.D dissertation, Kent Law School, University Of Kent 2006) p.333

³³ Consent by a male figure is not limited to abortion cases alone, but to all other forms of medical procedures.

³⁴ Titilayo Aderibigbe 'Women's Rights: Law and Practice in Nigeria' in Layi Erinsho; Babatunde Osotimehin and Janice E. Olawoye Women's Empowerment and Reproductive Health (Nigeria: Social Sciences and Reproductive Health Research Network, 1996), 48-49

³⁵ Ibid

³⁶ This is the heading of Section 5.3 of the 'National Policy on Population for Development, Unity, Progress and Self-reliance': Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1988.

³⁷ Ibid Section 5.3. The language of the policy statement is paternalistic, it gives the assumption that choice of family size is made by men to the exclusion of women who bear and nurture the children.

women would also not readily relinquish their right to choose when to procreate even when the directive is from their men.

The Criminal and Penal Codes do not make any provisions in respect of the rights of expectant fathers over a pregnancy for which they are responsible. It is imperative to state that the NPP statement is not conclusive as pointing to the right of expectant fathers to decide on abortion, because the statement is not law, but a policy directive by the Federal Government of Nigeria. Policy statements are the general plan of action by the maker for the person it is intended. The NPP is at best a plan of action by the Federal Government to State governments and citizens; it becomes law when it is promulgated as such. Policy statements have persuasive influence on State governments, but do not become law until they are made law, which then makes it binding on citizens.³⁸

It is apparent that the only persons Nigerian law gives a right of control over women's bodies in the case of abortion are medical doctors by virtue of section 279 of the Criminal Code.³⁹ The language of the National Population Policy echoes the perception of the male dominated government on the role of men in procreation, which tends to subsume women's right of control of their fertility into those of men. Women's interest in procreation is often believed by government from this statement to be secondary to men, even though women are the bearers and carers of children.⁴⁰ For procreation to take place, both men and women contribute equally in the formation of the foetus and once conception is completed, the burden of nurture continues within the confines of women's bodies for the next nine months of the pre-natal stage and for several years after delivery. Trying to control what happens to foetuses in vitro would amount to taking control of women's bodies. The government endorsed social order of patriarchy⁴¹ which gives the impression that patriarchy is reason enough for men to have control over women's body on the basis that 'the average man bears greater paternalistic burden in caring for the family'.⁴² Since men have been endorsed to determine family size, this means that men can also insist on women having abortions if they do not have the means to care for the child. Conversely, they may insist on women getting pregnant because they can maintain the child. Governments need to be cautious about encroaching upon the private lives of its citizens.

Having dealt with policy issues, what does the Nigerian law say on the rights of the expectant father in abortion? It is apparent that the sections of the Criminal and Penal Codes dealing with abortion are brief and do not comprehensively address present issues of abortion within the context of prevailing social circumstances; a careful reading of the sections in the codes are implicit enough to categorically state that the expectant father is not conferred with any

³⁸ Indeed many of the policy statements in the National Policy on Population have been made into law by many States such as giving a woman maternity leave with pay only after two years of a previous maternity leave.

³⁹ The Criminal Code Act, Cap C39, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004. Similar argument can be made under section 232 Penal Code because the language of both statute suggests that the choice is made by the doctor and not the pregnant woman which indirectly gives the doctor control over the woman's body, see Mary Boyle, *ReThinking Abortion: Psychology, gender, power and the law* (London and New York: Routledge, 1997), 71-73

⁴⁰ McLean states there have been battles between the two social groups of men and women over the control of women's fertility and procreative potentials: Sheila McLean, *A Woman's Right to Choose* (Rivers Oram, 1999 b), 6. It is submitted that the policy statement is evidence of the continued assumption of Nigerian government that it is men who 'take far reaching decisions including the family size', : Section 5:3, National Policy on Population For Development, Unity, Progress and Self-reliance': Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1988.

⁴¹ Section 5.3.1 of the National Policy on Population states: The patriarchal family system in the country shall be recognised for stability of the home'.

⁴² Ibid

right to contribute to or determine abortion. The pregnant woman herself is not conferred with such rights that are given only to the doctor.⁴³

In Nigeria, there has been no case of the expectant father exercising his right in abortion. This is indeed to be expected since abortion is a criminal offence whereby Nigerian courts as a former British colony, often refer to English decisions when deciding cases that have no precedence in Nigerian courts, therefore, even if an expectant father should seek to enforce his right over the foetus, the Nigerian courts are likely to reject it.⁴⁴ To do otherwise would be infringing on the rights of women as distinct and independent persons under the Constitution.⁴⁵ Where a Nigerian expectant father seeks to enforce an injunction against his partner to prevent her abortion using the acknowledged ground of patriarchy or using Article 4 of the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (as Paton did at the European Court of Human Rights);⁴⁶ the Nigerian courts would likely arrive at similar decisions at the High Court in *Paton v BPAS*⁴⁷ and the appellate court in *Paton v United Kingdom*.⁴⁸ In *Paton v BPAS* a husband sought to have an injunction against his wife to prevent her from having an abortion without his consent. The High Court stated that the expectant father had 'no legal right enforceable in law or equity to stop his wife having this abortion or to stop the doctor from carrying out the abortion'.⁴⁹ Furthermore, the court also stated citing *Montgomery v Montgomery*⁵⁰ that 'the court could only grant an injunction to support a legal right which the expectant father clearly does not have under law'.⁵¹ The Criminal and Penal Codes, the Nigerian Matrimonial Causes Act,⁵² the Constitution and the African Charter⁵³ do not give the expectant father the right to an injunction against his wife if a decision has been made by two doctors for the woman to have an abortion. Even where the expectant father is not married to the mother, the 'illegitimate father'⁵⁴ does not have a right to prevent abortion by the mother carrying their child.⁵⁵

Under Nigerian legislation, both sections 297 and 233 of the Criminal and Penal Codes respectively, do not give expectant fathers a right of consultation when an abortion is to be performed. Though, in practice, medical doctors would certainly inform the expectant father where abortion is performed legally to save the pregnant woman's life, however, it is not a legal requirement. This practice is obviously against the principle of medical confidentiality. But Nigerian doctors practice within their social and cultural environment and naturally conform to the patriarchal social system which is recognised by Schimidtke when he said that 'scientists are at least no better and no worse than the society of which they are members',⁵⁶ Nigerian doctors therefore conform to the social requirements of the society they live in which still believe that husbands have some interest in their wife's medical treatment and

⁴³ Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2004, Sections 297 Criminal Code and 232 Penal Code.

⁴⁴ As was done in *C v S* [1988] 1 All ER 1230

⁴⁵ Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended) section 34 (1).

⁴⁶ Where he used a similar Act under Article 2 of the European Convention of Human Rights

⁴⁷ *Paton v BPAS* [1978] 2 All ER 987.

⁴⁸ *Paton v United Kingdom* (1980) 3 EHRR.

⁴⁹ *Sir George Baker in Paton v BPAS* [1978] 2 All ER 987 at 988

⁵⁰ *Montgomery v Montgomery* [1964] 2 All ER 22 at 23.

⁵¹ *Paton v BPAS* [1978] 2 All ER 987 at 988.

⁵² Federal Republic of Nigeria, Matrimonial Causes Act, 1970, Section 71

⁵³ These are all laws in Nigeria that have provisions that guarantee the rights of individuals.

⁵⁴ *Per Sir George: Baker Paton v BPAS* [1978] 2 All ER 987, 990.

⁵⁵ In *C v S* [1979] GB 276 a putative father sought to prevent his girlfriend from carrying out an abortion and the court decided he had no legal right

⁵⁶ J. Schimidtke, 'Who owns the Human Genome? Ethical and Legal Aspects' *Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology* 44 (supplement 1) 205 at 205.

ought to be consulted. It is apparent that consultation does not detract from the fact that a wife or pregnant woman is a distinct individual and ought to have the ultimate choice to decide any form of medical treatment, including abortion without seeking consent from any other person. Not even her husband or expectant father.

Despite the absence of cases on the right of the expectant father in Nigeria on abortion, Nigerian courts would arrive at similar conclusions as British decisions even under the present law. The decision of Sir Baker in *Paton* can be used to support this assertion where he said: ‘Counsel have been unable to discover any extant decision in those countries whose laws derive from the common law that the consent of the husband is required before an otherwise legal abortion can be performed on the wife’.⁵⁷ Since Nigeria derived her laws from the Common Law, there is no legal requirement that a husband or expectant father is to be consulted when abortion decision is made by two medical practitioners. Furthermore, it is pertinent and imperative to state that even in custody proceedings, where it is acknowledged that patriarchy gives ownership of children to their father; the Nigerian courts do not consider the interest of the father as being superior to that of the mother.⁵⁸ The only recognisable right fathers have in law in Nigeria is that ‘the husband has a right to have a say in the destiny of the child he conceived’,⁵⁹ but that is only after the child is born and given legal recognition.⁶⁰

Paton appealed to the European Convention of Human Rights (ECHR) where he challenged the British Court’s decision on the basis that it infringed upon the right of the foetus to life under Article 2⁶¹ and his own right to family life under Article 8.⁶² He again failed. The European court reiterated that any foetal right to life is subordinated to the health of the pregnant woman, even though the foetus is not a person until it is born. Under Article 8, the court stated that it was the woman’s right to family life that is being decided and not *Paton*’s.

Similarly, Nigerian courts would likely hold that pregnant women’s rights as independent human beings under Article 4 of the African Charter⁶³ and section 33 of the Constitution⁶⁴ must be recognised and respected above that of the foetus they carry. Especially since Section 27 of the Criminal Code categorically stipulates that, a child does not have legal recognition until it is completely expelled from its mother’s body.⁶⁵ In the same vein a Nigerian expectant father’s argument that a doctor’s decision to perform an abortion on his partner without his consent would likely not be upheld because it is the right to family life of the pregnant woman that is paramount and not that of the expectant father.

⁵⁷ *Paton v BPAS* [1978] 2 All ER 987 at 992.

⁵⁸ *Theresa Williams v Rasheed Williams*, [1987] 2 NWLR (Part 54), 56, Supreme Court of Nigeria.

⁵⁹ *Ibid*

⁶⁰ Matrimonial Causes Act 1970 Section 71 gives equal rights to both parents in custody proceedings but the paramount consideration is the interest of the child concerned. But Nwogugu opines that this is only legal semantics because the right of the Nigerian father to custody is only in abeyance if custody is given to the mother. Eventually custody will revert to the father when the child is old enough for social reasons. E I Nwogugu *Family Law in Nigeria* (Nigeria, London: Heinemann Educational Books, 1974) 260. But my view on this is based on Section 39 of the Nigerian Constitution which guarantees equality of all people, and Article 18(3) of the African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights, which stipulates non-discrimination against women; the court ought to be able to give custody to the mother if it is in the best interest of the child and not to the father in future simply because of social practice under patriarchy

⁶¹ African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights, Article 2 guarantees everyone’s right to life

⁶² African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights, Article 8 guarantees a citizen’s right to family life.

⁶³ Article 4 African Charter of Human and Peoples’ Rights 1979

⁶⁴ The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as Amended) Cap. C23 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 1999 S. 33

⁶⁵ Section 307 Criminal Code Act, & Section 5(2) Penal Code, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria,

The above cited judicial decisions which do not recognise the right of the expectant father or male spouse in the abortion decision appear to have opened another legal controversy concerning the inequality between man and woman with respect to decision concerning abortion. An expectant father is said to have no right to object to termination of pregnancy even though he is involved in its conception. Ironically, the same law imposes on the father the liability for child support on the basis that he was involved in the conception.

SUGGESTIONS

It is apparent from the judicial approach worldwide that as much as abortion is concerned, the expectant father, for practical reasons, has no rights. For this singular reason, this worldwide negative attitude to the right of the anxious father will definitely continue. This position seems inappropriate, it is therefore suggested that an expectant father should be vested with the rights to be informed or consulted irrespective of the reasons for the abortion procedure. A balance must be struck especially where it does not relate to the health or life of the pregnant mother. If it is health related, the right of the pregnant woman should outweigh the right of the expectant father because it is apparent that it is the woman who carries the fetus for nine months and whose health and life are mainly at risk during that time. It is crystal clear that this factor explains the legal and judicial negative attitudes to the rights of the expectant father over his foetus. An expectant father who objects to the abortion procedure may well deserve sympathy but at the end, a pregnant woman's right over her body must take precedence.

In essence, the pregnant woman should reserve a right over her body, that is, she should be given the freedom to control her reproduction choice when it relates to health issues. Though with minimal interference by an expectant father. That is, when seeking abortion, an expectant father should be given a right to be consulted

There is need for a consensus to be reached between couples when the pregnant woman is married. Unmarried pregnant woman on the other hand has the freedom to make their own choices depending on the individual circumstances surrounding their pregnancy.

It is also proper and advisable that during the counselling and ascertaining the wishes of the woman taking abortion decision, that the husband be involved because much unhappiness may be saved if the decision is made jointly by both parties.

It is suggested that the state should acknowledge the mutual respect and relationship in the institution of marriage by precluding a woman in marriage from taking a unilateral decision to terminate the pregnancy. The state should recognise the fact that an expectant father is likely to have a special interest in his unborn child. It is unimaginable that the state should legally require the consent of both parties in case of adoption and fosterage but shy away from recognising the interest of the husband or expectant father in the abortion decision.

It is of the view that there may be exceptional circumstances or situations where the right of the pregnant woman would outweigh that of the expectant father in which abortion can be allowed without the consent of the expectant father but he is entitled to be informed or consulted, such as where pregnancy is due to rape, incest or as a result of exploitation of a young girl or a mentally incapacitated woman and where the pregnancy constitutes a risk to the life of the mother. Also, where there is likelihood of permanent injury to the health of the mother. There must be a balance of rights between the pregnant woman and the expectant father. Whereas the pregnant woman has a right of life. Hence, the law must try to create an appropriate equilibrium between the conflicting rights of the pregnant woman and the

expectant father. Even, given the fact that abortion is allowed where health or life of the pregnant woman is threatened, it presents a very narrow tolerance for abortion in Nigeria. It is suggested that scope of exceptions to abortion in Nigeria could be expanded based on the views expressed in this work.

In whole, it is submitted that the laws should not be used to debar the genuine interests of the woman and her reproductive rights, especially where her health or life is in danger of the continued pregnancy.

CONCLUSION

It is clear that in matters of abortion, the pregnant woman's right is paramount; she alone has the right to determine the fate of her foetus because this is rooted in the fact that she is the one primarily concerned with the pregnancy, its continuation or termination. More so her right to private life is in issue. To exclude the expectant father who has contributed to conception in the decision-making process is not altogether desirable, this position will be regarded as absurd and abnormal in traditional societies where men have proprietary patriarchal powers and rights over females. These rights extend to men's control over the foetus growing inside women's bodies. While the law ought to accord primary consideration to the right of the pregnant woman, the views of the expectant father should not be treated as irrelevant either. A man has right to father children and to enjoy the association of his offspring, on the basis of which he should have a say in an abortion decision. The maintenance of matrimonial harmony is compelling reason for a consensus resolution framework. Once a balance is struck, it will definitely take care of the interest of the expectant father in the abortion decision.